

SOME ARYL NAPHTHYL SULPHIDES AND SULPHONES

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The Fries isomerisation of α -naphthyl benzene-, *p*-toluene- and *o*-toluene-sulphonates is described. The resulting sulphones are shown to be *o*-hydroxysulphones from their ultraviolet absorption spectra as well as wet and dry melting points. Methyl α -naphthyl ether condenses with arenesulphonyl chlorides in the presence of anhydrous stannic chloride to furnish aryl 4-methoxynaphthyl sulphones.

In a recent publication (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 391), we reported the isomerisation of sulpho- nates derived from β -naphthol. In the present communication the results of the isomerisation of α -naphthyl benzene-, *o*-toluene- and *p*-toluene-sulphonates are presented.

The sulphonates (I) on treatment with anhydrous aluminium chloride at 160° for three hours underwent rearrangement to afford small amounts of alkali-soluble products. In each case only one hydroxysulphone could be isolated from the reaction mixture. The product can be *o*-hydroxysulphone (II) or *p*-hydroxysulphone (III).

[Ar = Ph, *p*-Tol or *o*-Tol]

To establish the identity of the Fries product, the *o*- and *p*-isomers were sought to be synthesised by unambiguous methods. For the synthesis of the *o*-hydroxysulphones (II), the following scheme was attempted. The conversion of the aminosulphone to the hydroxy compound was, however, not successful.

[Ar = Ph, *o*-Tol or *p*-Tol]

The *p*-hydroxysulphones were easily obtained by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of methyl α -naphthyl ether with arenesulphonyl chlorides (cf. Leandri and Maioli, *Ann. chim.*, 1955, 45, 3; *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, 49, 15785) and by subsequent demethylation of the products. The identity of the sulphones thus obtained was established by condensing 1-bromo-4-methoxynaphthalene with appropriate thiophenols and oxidising the resulting sulphides. The demethylated sulphones were found to be different from those obtained by the Fries isomerisation of α -naphthyl arene-sulphonates. This ruled out the possibility of the Fries products being *p*-hydroxysulphones.

That the Fries products are *o*-hydroxysulphones was also borne out by a consideration of their wet and dry melting points. The depression in melting point, when wet, is large for asso-

ciated compounds while it is small for chelated molecules. Amstutz *et al.* (*Science*, 1950, 111, 305) have indeed employed this method to show that chelation exists in *o*-hydroxysulphones.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Table I shows the differences in the dry and wet melting points of the sulphones obtained by the isomerisation of α -naphthyl sulphonates. For comparison, the differences in the dry and wet melting points of the synthetic *p*-hydroxysulphones are also shown. The data clearly indicate that the Fries products are *o*-hydroxysulphones.

TABLE I

Compound	Dry m.p.	Wet m.p.	Diff.
Fries product from α -naphthyl benzenesulphonate	132°	126°	6°
Fries product from α -naphthyl <i>o</i> -toluenesulphonate	119°	114°	5°
Fries product from α -naphthyl <i>p</i> -toluenesulphonate	134°	129°	5°
1-Hydroxy-4-naphthyl phenyl sulphone	170°	112°	58°
1-Hydroxy-4-naphthyl <i>o</i> -tolyl sulphone	168°	111°	57°
1-Hydroxy-4-naphthyl <i>p</i> -tolyl sulphone	129°	97°	32°

The ultraviolet spectral data (Table II) also lead to the same conclusion. In diphenyl sulphone, the principal absorption band is at 235 $m\mu$ ($\epsilon_{\max}$ 17,400). In *o*-hydroxydiphenyl sulphone this band undergoes a slight hypsochromic shift with decrease in the intensity of absorption ($\lambda_{\max}$ 233 $m\mu$, $\epsilon_{\max}$ 12,600). In *p*-hydroxydiphenyl sulphone there is a bathochromic shift

of this band ($\lambda_{\max}$ 256 $m\mu$, $\epsilon_{\max}$ 16,000). A similar behaviour is seen with the naphthalene derivatives listed in Table II (see also Figs. 1-4). If it is assumed that the Fries products are *o*-hydroxysulphones, their absorption spectra exhibit a hypsochromic shift, when compared to the absorption spectra of the parent sulphones (β -naphthyl phenyl sulphone and β -naphthyl *p*-tolyl sulphone). On the other hand, the spectra of the *p*-hydroxysulphones may be seen to exhibit a bathochromic shift, when compared to the spectra of the parent sulphones (α -naphthyl phenyl sulphone and α -naphthyl *p*-tolyl sulphone).

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

TABLE II
(Spectra in 95% ethanol)

Compound.	* $\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.
β -Naphthyl phenyl sulphone	240 $m\mu$	46,000
	218	36,000
Fries product from α -naphthyl benzenesulphonate	237	29,000
	218	34,100
β -Naphthyl <i>p</i> -tolyl sulphone	244	39,400
	222	37,400
Fries product from α -naphthyl <i>p</i> -toluenesulphonate	239	27,700
	220	35,700
α -Naphthyl phenyl sulphone	231	28,300
	219	35,000
1-Hydroxy-4-naphthyl phenyl sulphone	236	37,600
α -Naphthyl <i>p</i> -tolyl sulphone	† (232)	30,200
	† (220)	34,400
1-Hydroxy-4-naphthyl <i>p</i> -tolyl sulphone	235	37,800

* Only the high intensity bands are given.

† Shoulders are shown in parentheses.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Naphthyl *o*-toluenesulphonate was obtained by treatment of α -naphthol with *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in the presence of ethanolic KOH. It crystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 115-16°. (Found: C, 68.34; H, 4.53. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.73%.)

Fries Rearrangement of α -Naphthyl Sulphonates.—The procedure adopted was the same as reported earlier (*loc. cit.*). The sulphonates, which were isomerised, and the products obtained are indicated in Table III. In ethanolic solution, the hydroxysulphonates exhibit a green colour with ferric chloride.

TABLE III

Sulphonate.	%Yield.	Formula.	M.P.	Hydroxysulphonate.			
				%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
α -Naphthyl benzene-	12	$C_{16}H_{12}O_2S$	131-32°	67.36	67.62	4.71	4.22
α -Naphthyl <i>p</i> -toluene-	10	$C_{17}H_{14}O_2S$	133-34°	68.39	68.45	5.00	4.73
α -Naphthyl <i>o</i> -toluene-	2	$C_{17}H_{14}O_2S$	118-19°	68.21	68.45	4.57	4.73

1-Amino-2-naphthylphenyl Sulphone.—1-Nitro-2-naphthyl phenyl sulphone (5 g.) (Neumoyer and Amstutz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1680) was suspended in water (100 c.c.). Iron filings (10 g.) and ferrous sulphate (5 g.) were added to the above, the mixture refluxed for 90 minutes, and poured into water. The solid residue was extracted with ethanol, when, pale yellow needles separated (4.3 g.). It was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 144-45°. The above reduction was not successful with tin and HCl (conc.).

2-Chloro-1-nitronaphthalene was condensed with *p*-thiocresol and *o*-thiocresol. The nitrosulphides obtained were oxidised to the nitrosulphonates with H_2O_2 and then reduced to the amino-sulphonates. The relevant data regarding these compounds are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Compound.	%Yield.	Formula.	M.P.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
α -1-Nitro-2-naphthylphenyl S*	90	$C_{16}H_{11}O_2NS$	59°(a)	..	..	..	..
1-Nitro-2-naphthyl phenyl S*	100	$C_{16}H_{11}O_2NS$	149°(b)	..	..	..	..
1-Amino-2-naphthyl phenyl S'	86	$C_{16}H_{13}O_2NS$	144-45°(a)	67.78	67.84	4.80	4.60
1-Nitro-2-naphthyl <i>p</i> -tolyl S*	80	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2NS$	105°(a)	..	..	..	..
1-Nitro-2-naphthyl <i>p</i> -tolyl S'	100	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2NS$	173°(b)	62.70	62.37	3.77	4.00
1-Amino-2-naphthyl <i>p</i> -tolyl S'	60	$C_{17}H_{15}O_2NS$	164-65°(a)	68.63	68.66	5.16	5.09
1-Nitro-2-naphthyl <i>o</i> -tolyl S	85	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2NS$	123°(a)	69.34	69.13	4.65	4.44
1-Nitro-2-naphthyl <i>o</i> -tolyl S'	100	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2NS$	127-28°(b)	62.50	62.37	4.19	4.00
1-Amino-2-naphthyl <i>o</i> -tolyl S'	90	$C_{17}H_{15}O_2NS$	134-135°(a)	68.77	68.66	5.08	5.09

N.B. S and S' denote respectively sulphide and sulphone.

(a) Crystallised from ethanol, (b) crystallised from acetic acid.

* Neumoyer and Amstutz, *loc. cit.*

4-Methoxy-1-naphthylphenyl Sulphide.—To dry sodium phenyl sulphide (obtained from 0.8 g. of sodium and 3.7 g. of thiophenol) were added 4-bromo-1-methoxynaphthalene (8 g.) (Szmuz-covicz and Modest, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 566) and copper powder (0.5 g.). The mixture was heated at 220-40° for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was then steam-distilled after adding

zinc dust (2 g.) and H_2SO_4 (1 : 1 ; 25 c.c.). The semisolid residue was extracted with ethanol and recrystallised from the same solvent in pale white crystals, m.p. 87-88°, yield 77%. (Found : C, 75.97 ; H, 5.22. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}OS$: C, 76.67 ; H, 5.30%). Leandri and Maioli (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 72°.

4-Methoxy-1-naphthylphenyl Sulphone.—Oxidation of the above sulphide in acetic acid with excess of 5% $KMnO_4$ solution furnished the sulphone. On crystallisation from acetic acid, it melted at 194-95°. (Found : C, 67.66 ; H, 4.45. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}O_2S$: C, 68.42 ; H, 4.73%).

4-Hydroxy-1-naphthylphenyl Sulphone.—The foregoing compound (1 g.) was demethylated by refluxing with hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7 ; 10 c.c.) at 170-80° for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water, the solid obtained was washed with water, and digested with a 10% solution of $NaOH$. The alkali extract on acidification furnished the hydroxysulphone in 60% yield. It crystallised from ethanol as colorless plates, m.p. 169-70°. (Found : C, 67.57 ; H, 4.26. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 67.57 ; H, 4.64%). It develops a green colour with ferric chloride.

Friedel-Crafts' Reaction of Methyl α -Naphthyl Ether with *p*-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride.—From methyl α -naphthyl ether (5.3 g.) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (6.5 g.) and using anhydrous stannic chloride as catalyst, the methoxysulphone was obtained in 60% yield. The compound crystallised from acetic acid as tiny plates, m.p. 203-204°, not depressed by an admixture with a synthetic sample of 4-methoxy-1-naphthyl *p*-tolyl sulphone. (Found : C, 69.45 ; H, 5.56. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 69.20 ; H, 5.16%).

4-Methoxy-1-naphthyl-*p*-tolyl sulphide was prepared in 60% yield from 4-bromo-1-methoxy-naphthalene (8 g.) and dry sodium *p*-tolyl sulphide (5 g.). Repeated recrystallisation from ethanol gave fine, colorless needles, m.p. 102-103°. (Found : C, 76.67 ; H, 6.37. $C_{18}H_{14}OS$ requires C, 77.13 ; H, 5.75%).

4-Methoxy-1-naphthyl-*p*-tolyl Sulphone.—Oxidation of the above sulphide with aqueous $KMnO_4$ furnished the sulphone in 60% yield. It crystallised as flat needles from acetic acid, m.p. 202-204°. (Found : C, 68.92 ; H, 4.92. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 69.20 ; H, 5.16%).

4-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl-*p*-tolyl Sulphone.—Demethylation of the foregoing methoxysulphone with hydriodic acid in the usual way gave the hydroxysulphone in 60% yield. It crystallised from ethanol as fine needles, m.p. 128-29°. (Found : C, 68.98 ; H, 4.83. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 68.45 ; H, 4.73%). It exhibits a green colour with ferric chloride.

Friedel-Crafts' Reaction of Methyl α -Naphthyl Ether with *o*-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride.—Methyl α -naphthyl ether (5.3 g.) and *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (6.5 g.) gave the methoxy sulphone in 60% yield (6 g.). Two crystallisations from acetic acid gave fine, colorless needles, m.p. 195-96°. (Found : C, 69.52 ; H, 5.10. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 69.20 ; H, 5.16%).

4-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl-*o*-tolyl Sulphone.—Demethylation of the above sulphone furnished the hydroxysulphone in 60% yield. It crystallised as shining plates from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 167-68°. (Found : C, 68.16 ; H, 4.64. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 68.45 ; H, 4.73%). It shows a green colour with ferric chloride.

Ultraviolet Absorption Measurements.—The spectra were determined using a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, Model DU. The solvent used was 95% ethanol.